

2. Ethidium bromide staining of PCR products for RG118 (A), RG13 (C) and RG235 (E) loci amplified from total genomic DNA of Iranian varieties and restriction fragments generated from the products digested with *MvaI* (B) and *HinfI* (D). The numbers for each lane are the entry numbers used in Figure 1. The approximate size of bands is shown in the base pair.

than to indicas. Despite their very typical indica morphology (long and cylindrical seed, tall stature, narrow leaves), these varieties, as well as some of the Champa-type varieties, are clustered with standard japonicas. This suggests that the morphological characteristics are not representative of the genetic status of a given variety, and as revealed by Glaszmann (1987), these varieties may belong to isozyme group V

and are therefore neither pure indica nor pure japonica.

We found PCR-based RFLP to be faster, easier, and relatively cheaper than Southern-based RFLP. PCR markers are now abundant, with known map locations. Their application is highly reproducible and more informative than randomly amplified polymorphic DNA.

Cited references

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Distribution and evolutionary differentiation of mitochondrial plasmidlike DNAs in the genus *Oryza*

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We investigated the distribution of plasmidlike DNAs homologous to those of *O. sativa* in the genus *Oryza* and found some evolutionary differentiations of plasmidlike DNAs. Four kinds of circular mitochondrial plasmid-like DNAs, designated B1, B2, B3, and B4, have been detected in many *Oryza sativa* strains and analyzed in DNA sequences.

We first analyzed the distribution of plasmidlike DNAs homologous to those of *O. sativa* in 40 strains of the genus *Oryza* with AA, BB, BBCC, CC, CCDD, and EE genomes (Miyata et al 1995). Using the B1, B2, B3, and B4 clones as probes, plasmidlike DNAs were observed only in varieties with AA, CC, and CCDD genomes. The distribution patterns of strains with the AA genome were highly polymorphic. This suggests that the disappearance of plasmidlike DNAs occurred during the diversification of strains with the AA genome.

We then amplified the plasmidlike DNAs from strains with the AA genome by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and examined restriction fragment length polymorphisms (RFLPs). RFLPs were detected among plasmidlike DNAs amplified from different strains (Miyata et al 1995), indicating some mutations, such as base substitutions.

In CC and CCDD genomes, some signals hybridized with the B1 probe showed rather different restriction patterns, indicating that these signals are new plasmidlike DNAs homologous to B1. We cloned them and named them M1, M2, and M3. Their entire nucleotide sequences were determined; M1 is 2,430 bp in size, M2 is 2,034 bp, and M3 is 2,096 bp. We compared each of these sequences and found that M1, M2, and M3 share high homology to B1. B1, M2, and M3 each lack about 300 bp of a region that is present in M1, and small repeats were found at the sites of deleted sequences (see figure).

We therefore propose the hypothesis that the B1 family differentiated from a common ancient molecule that was similar to M1 through slipped mispairing during DNA replication at several stages in the evolution in the genus *Oryza*.

The schematic representation of the explanation for the generation of members of the B1 family of mitochondrial plasmidlike DNAs during the diversification of the genus *Oryza*^a.

^aShaded portions indicate M1 and the regions homologous to M1. Large arrows indicate the differentiation of the B1 family. The dashed lines of A, B, and C indicate the deleted regions of M1 and the corresponding sites in B1, M2, and M3, respectively. White and black arrowheads indicate the small repeats of 3 bp and 15 bp at the deleted sites of A and B, respectively.

Cited reference

Miyata S, Kanazawa A, Tsutsumi N, Sano Y, Hirai A. 1995. Polymorphic distribution and molecular diversification of mitochondrial plasmid-like DNAs in the genus *Oryza*. *Jpn. J. Genet.* (in press.) ■

Genetic diversity of Chinese wild rice populations

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The genetic diversity of Chinese rice *Oryza rufipogon* and its relationships with the strains distributed in tropical Asia have not been fully investigated.

We examined three samples from populations collected in southern China from Dongxiang, Jiangxi (DX, the northernmost site of this species), Yuangjing, Yunnan (YJ), and Guigang, Guangxi (GG) for

various phenotypic characters, isozymes, and nuclear genome restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP). Four populations collected from Thailand, India, and Indonesia were used as the controls. A total of 292 plants were examined.

O. rufipogon is differentiated into two types: perennial and annual (often referred to as *O. nivara*). We have found Chinese wild rices that are perennial, but they tend to differ from the typical perennial type from tropical countries in terms of root and shoot regeneration pattern from basal nodes, dry weight proportion of newly emerged tillers after heading, and panicle number per plant.

The result of factor analysis based on 11 characters indicated that the populations examined, though they contained intra-population variability, showed inter-population differentiation into annual and perennial types. Chinese populations were

intermediate between the annual and perennial types.

Polymorphism was found in 29 isozyme loci and 15 probe/restriction enzyme combinations. Differences among populations seemed to be clearer in RFLP than in isozyme variation. Chinese populations share some common markers that are rarely found in other populations, indicating that they differ from one another (Table 1). The result of factor analysis of isozyme data revealed geographic variation, but not ecological variation (perennial vs annual differentiation).

Interestingly, populations of Chinese rice *O. rufipogon* contain some "japonica-specific alleles," such as *Est-13(t)-1* and *Cat1-2*, at higher frequencies than in other populations (Table 1). At other loci, however, they carry some "indica-specific alleles," as in other populations.

Table 1. Allelic frequencies at six isozyme loci and four RFLP markers.

Locus/allele	Population						
	China			Thailand		Indonesia	India
	DX P ^a	YJ P	GG P	NE3 A	NE88 P	W1981 P	W120 P
<i>Isozyme</i>							
<i>Sdh1-2</i>	0.90	0.89	0.92	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.68
<i>Amp1-3</i>	1.00	1.00	0.96	0.00	0.04	0.50	0.43
<i>Acp7 (t)-1</i>	1.00	1.00	0.81	0.19	0.33	0.56	0.21
<i>Est9-1</i>	0.92	0.47	0.29	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.07
<i>Est13 (t)-1</i>	0.98	1.00	0.59	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
<i>Cat1-2</i>	0.99	1.00	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.25
<i>RFLP</i>							
G282-2 ²	0.65	1.00	0.10	0.00	0.07	-	-
G187-1 ²	1.00	1.00	0.96	0.65	0.01	-	0.64
G20-2 ⁰	1.00	0.65	0.63	0.00	0.00	-	-
G249-1 ²	0.65	1.00	0.78	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00

^aP = perennial, A = annual.

Table 2. Parameter values showing intrapopulation genetic diversity estimated from data of 29 isozyme loci and 15 RFLP markers.

Parameter	Population						
	DX	YJ	GG	NE3	NE88	W1981	W120
<i>Isozyme</i>							
(no. of plants examined)	54	14	68	74	46	22	14
Av gene diversity (\bar{H})	0.07	0.04	0.20	0.14	0.21	0.22	0.25
Proportion of polymorphic loci	0.55	0.10	0.83	0.41	0.69	0.55	0.59
Alleles/locus (av no.)	1.55	1.10	2.10	1.45	1.97	1.72	1.75
Frequency of heterozygote	0.13	0.14	0.53	0.07	0.46	0.46	0.71
<i>RFLP</i>							
(no. of plants examined)	46	14	63	74	41	-	-
Av gene diversity (\bar{H})	0.13	0.19	0.27	0.20	0.12	-	-
Proportion of polymorphic loci	0.31	0.46	0.73	0.53	0.60	-	-
Alleles/locus (av no.)	1.38	1.46	1.80	1.53	1.67	-	-
Frequency of heterozygote	0.54	0.00	0.30	0.03	0.27	-	-